

Socio-cultural plants used by the Moyon Naga Tribe of Manipur, Northeastern India

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Abstract

Moyon Naga tribe is one of the recognized tribes of Manipur. The study deals with 75 plant species from 32 families of socio-cultural plant (SCP) used by Moyon was documented. The SCP includes food, medicine, spice, traditional house construction, shampoo and detergent, traditional drinks and beverages, handicraft, fishing, fencing, ornamental plant, fibres, etc. Plants and their parts used by Moyon tribe in SCP ranges from stem (13), leaves (12), fruit (11), whole plant (10) and least one in case petiole and grain (1). In case of plant habit highest was recorded in shrubs (33), 17 and 15 in tree and climber respectively and found lowest in creeper (1). The study is a unique one and first of its kind so as to validate and to take up conservation steps for sustainable use in future.

Keywords: Moyon tribe; Socio-cultural plants; Plant parts; Habitat; Conservation and Sustainable use

1. Introduction

Moyon Naga tribe is one of the recognized tribes of Manipur with distinct identity, rich traditions and cultural heritages passed down from generation to generation [1]. Compared to other tribes *Moyon* tribes are very thinly populated. According to the Census of India 2011, the total population of the Moyon is 2516 with 581 households. The male population is 1,172 and female is 1,344. Sex ratio is 1177, child sex ratio is 975 [1].

Not much is known except a very few publications have contributed on ethnobotanical studies from the Chandel district of Manipur. ethno-botanically important plant species (523) from Tengnoupal district, Manipur was reported [2]. Forty-five (45) species of ichthyotoxic plants within 21 families used for fishing was reported [3]. A total of 68 wild edible vegetables belonging to 42 families were documented which are being used by indigenous communities for nutritive and therapeutic purposes [4].

The literacy rate of Moyon is 84% with 88.5 for male and 80.2 for female. Their neighbouring tribes are *Anal*, *Maring*, *Kuki*, *Monshang*, *Tarao*, *Aimol*, *Lamkang* and *Chothe*. The *Moyons* are fond of merry making and relish good food as indicated in the form of festivals. They love bright colours as can be seen from their traditional shawls and other clothes woven with different patterns by looms. Traditional dresses and ornaments made of shells and bones of animals and plants products were worn and come out for dance during festivals. The *Moyons* have a very close bond among them, united by their unique culture and tradition [1].

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There is not much work done on ethnobotanical studies among the *Moyon* community. Therefore, an urgent call for extensive research and documentation on ethnomedicinal perspectives of the *Moyon-Naga* tribe which is the need of the hour.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Collection of Information

Information of various ethnobotanically important plants were collected with the permission of the village authority and seniors, their utilization patterns were noted periodically, based on the validation of the uses and a short description, updated correct botanical name of plants with valuable data used by Moyon tribe were developed and documented. Intensive ethnobotanical survey was conducted during the tenure of the research programme 2020 to 2023, among the people of Moyon-Naga tribe for gathering information on ethnobotanically important plants (wild edible plants, medicinal plants, socio-cultural plants, etc.) which are traditionally used by them. The authenticity of the uses was repeatedly verified by asking to the different informers through questionnaires. The details were recorded in the information sheets.

2.2. Study Site

Manipur, one of the important biodiversity hot spot lies in the northeastern corner of India. The Moyon (Bujuur in local dialect) are one of the earliest settlers of the state of Manipur and settled in the district of Chandel and few in the border areas of Myanmar. One of the smallest tribes in the states of Manipur with a population of a little over 2689 (Publicity & information Secretary, BAP–Moyon Apex body), the Moyon tribes settled in 17 villages, namely: 1. Kapaam (Komlathabi) village, 2. Nungthar (Penaching) village, 3. Tungphae (Heigrutampak) Village, 4. Khukthar village, 5. Mangkang village, 6. Khurfhuwdam village, 7. Kuurkam village, 8. Khuwring village, 9. Sinadam village, 10. Thangkin village, 11. Chumthar village, 12. Khungjuur village, 13. Mitong village, 14. Laarfuw village, 15. Rashangkhar Village, 16. Moyon Khullen village, 17. Ringkum [Figure 1].

Figure 1 Map of Study Sites: India and Manipur map, showing the Moyon inhabited areas in Chandel (Light pink) and Tengnoupal Districts of Manipur. Study sites plotting by black spots

2.3. Identification of plant sample

The field survey was conducted in the respective localities and the plant materials are collected by the following the standard method [5]. Plants were identified with the expert team of the Botanical Survey of India (BSI, Shillong) and experts of Forest Department. One set of herbarium specimens was pre-identified at Manipur University Museum of Plants (MUMP), Life Sciences Department, Manipur University, Imphal, and their accession numbers were checked and authenticated. The same herbarium was further checked at Botanical Survey of India, Eastern Circle Shillong, and deposited to the herbarium of the Department of Botany, Royal Global University, Guwahati.

2.4. Detail Methods to Display

In case of contradictory information, efforts will be made to get the correct information. Regular surveys were conducted following the questionnaire at the selected local vegetables, medicinal etc., markets of the 16 villages at least twice in a month [6]. A total of 104 women informants were interviewed regarding the local name of the leafy vegetables, their use for instance as medicinal, edible, etc., source and market price [1]. Voucher specimens were processed and mounted herbarium sheets [5]. The plants were identified with the help of different published literatures [6,7,8, 9], [10,11,12, 13], [14 – 19].

3. Results and discussion

In the present study, 75 species from 32 different families of socio-cultural plants used by the *Moyon* is documented. The used of plants includes food, medicine, spice, traditional house construction, shampoo and detergent, traditional drinks and beverages, handicraft, fishing, fencing, ornamental plant, fibres, etc. The plant parts used include stem, leaves, flowers, fruits, root, culm, rhizome, seed, grain, tuber, etc. is tabulated in Table 1.

These plants were categorized according to the number of plants as shrubs (33), Tree (17), climbers (15), herbs (9), Creeper (1) respectively Figure 3. Plant part used are stem (13), leaves (12), fruit (11), whole plant (10), bark (5), culm (5), seed (4), rhizome (4), flower (4), tuber (3), root (2), petiole (1), grain (1) in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Among the 32 families Poaceae (8) was found highest and lowest was recorded as 1 (one) in the families Araceae, Apiaceae, Asteraceae, Cannaceae, Costaceae, Ericaceae, Gnetaceae, Juglandaceae, Oxalidaceae, Pinaceae, Rubiaceae, Saururaceae, Theaceae, and Verbenaceae [Table 1].

However, the following families were recorded along with their numbers as follows: Malvaceae (6), Arecaceae (5), Zingiberaceae (5), Dioscoreaceae, Fabaceae, Musaceae, Rutaceae (4), Lauraceae (3), Lamiaceae (3), Anacardiaceae (2), Acanthaceae (2), Apocynaceae (2), Euphorbiaceae(2), Fabaceae(2), Pedaliaceae (2), Solanaceae (2) [Table 1].

From the above observation it clear that there are many socio-religious plants still in record used in various socio-religious events of Moyon tribe of Manipur.

Table 1 Plants used by *Moyon* tribe in Socio-cultural importance

Sl. No.	Botanical Name	Local Name	Family	Life form	Part used	Uses
1	<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kurz	Taetoo	Anacardiaceae	Tree	leaves	The crushed leaves are boiled and used as shampoo to treat dandruff and hair fall
2	<i>Rhus chinensis</i> Mill.	Khomah	Anacardiaceae	Tree	fruits	The fruit is boiled and used as traditional herbal drinks after the food for digestion
3	<i>Alocasia macrorrhizos</i> (L.) G.Don.	Bathuong	Araceae	shrub	Petiole	The petiole is used as an important ingredient in fermentation of fish called 'Ngathuw' relished by the Moyon.
4	<i>Eryngium foetidum</i> L.	Basumaro	Apiaceae	Herbs	Leaves	The fresh leaf is used as spice in curry. Controls BP and anti-inflammatory
5	<i>Calamus latifolius</i> Roxb.	Echiing	Arecaceae	climber	Stem	The mature stem harvested are used for tying the frames and pillars in construction of houses. It is also used in making baskets. The young shoots and fruits are edible

6	<i>Calamus floribundus</i> Griff.	<i>Echiing ynror</i>	Arecaceae	climber	Stem	Used in making baskets and other handicraft and robe in construction of house
7	<i>Calamus jenkinsianus</i> Griff.	<i>Echiing edii</i>	Arecaceae	limber	Stem	Used in making baskets and other handicraft and robe in construction of house
8	<i>Calamus leptospadix</i> Griff.	<i>Echiing aanruw</i>	Arecaceae	climber	Stem	Used in making baskets and other handicraft and robe in construction of house
9	<i>Calamus tenuis</i> Roxb.	<i>Echiing</i>	Arecaceae	climber	Stem	Used in making baskets and other handicraft and robe in construction of house
10	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	<i>Paarchiip ivaar</i>	Acanthaceae	Shrub	Whole plant	Used as fencing and used as medicine
11	<i>Phlogacanthus thysiformis</i> (Roxb. ex Hardw.) D. J. Mabberley	<i>Paarchiip</i>	Acanthaceae	shrub	Whole plant	Used as fencing & also as medicine for controlling blood pressure.
12	<i>Dendrobium chrysotoxum</i> Lindl.	<i>Keenthangrii</i>	Apocynaceae	herb	Flower	The ladies adorn the flower on their ear or pinned on their hair on all socio-cultural functions.
13	<i>Dendrobium infudibulum</i> Lindl.	<i>Phuurva (orchid)</i>	Apocynaceae	herb	Fleshy stem	The ladies adorn the flower on their ear or pinned on their hair on all socio-cultural functions. The succulent stem is cut and applied on the cracked heels to heal.
14	<i>Tagetes erecta</i> L.	<i>Tomarii</i>	Asteraceae	Shrub	Whole plant	Used as insect repellent. The crushed leaves are applied on the injured wound to stop bleeding and infection.
15	<i>Canna indica</i> L.		Cannaceae	shrub	Flower	Ornamental flower – the ladies adorn the flower on their ear or pinned on their hair on all socio-cultural functions.
16	<i>Cheilocostus speciosus</i> (J.Konig) C.Specht	<i>Ruwuum</i>	Costaceae	shrub	Whole plants	Bark of stem are crushed juice is used as shampoo. The juice is also used as anti-diabetic
17	<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	<i>Barah</i>	Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Tuber	The tuber is boiled and eat as food during famine
18	<i>Dioscorea japonica</i> Thunb.	<i>Rampa barah</i>	Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Tuber	The tuber is boiled and eat as food during famine
19	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	<i>Reengkheer</i>	Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Fruit	The fruit is boiled and eat as food during famine
20	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i> L.	<i>Rampa barah edii</i>	Dioscoreaceae	climber	Tuber	The tuber is boiled and eat as food during famine
21	<i>Rhododendron arboretum</i> Sm.	<i>Ruwshopaar</i>	Ericaceae	Tree	Flowers	The inflorescence/ flower is adorned by ladies on their ear lobes or pinned on their hair during traditional function and festivals. The extract of flower juice is given to

						patients with liver complains and anaemic condition
22	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	<i>shaeruw</i>	Phyllanthaceae	Tree	Fruit	Fresh fruit is boiled with rice water for about 10-15 mins and is used for hair wash. Fresh fruit juice is mixed with sesame oil and is applied to the scalp for long black hair.
23	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	<i>Tengnu</i>	Euphorbiaceae	shrub	Whole plant	The succulent shrub with thorns on the stem is grown along with bamboo species in heterogenous fencing.
24	<i>Albizia myriophylla</i> Benth.	<i>jaeruw</i>	Fabaceae	Climber	stem	The rice powder is mixed with the bark powder of the jaeruw and kneaded with water to make into cake and dry. It becomes a yeast and uses in preparation of 'Zuw'
25	<i>Senegalia rugata</i> (Lam.) Britton & Rose	<i>Ruwphoph</i>	Fabaceae	Woody Climber	Bark of stem	The stem is crushed, and the extract juice is used to poison fishes during community fishing. The paste of the leaves and bark is used as shampoo
26	<i>Castanopsis armata</i> (Roxb.) Spach	<i>Ruwshii</i>	Fabaceae	Tree	Stem & nuts	The stem is used as pillar for construction of house
27	<i>Entada gigas</i> (L.) Fawc & Rendle	<i>Ruwshii/kongkra</i>	Fabaceae	climber	stem	The stem is split and used in tying the frames and pillar in construction of traditional house.
28	<i>Gnetum montanum</i> Markgraf.	<i>Iriih</i>	Gnetaceae	Woody climber	Whole plant	The stem is crushed, and the extract juice is used to poison fishes. The leaves are used for fish preservation.
29	<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	<i>Mangkha</i>	Juglandaceae	Tree	Stem & nuts	The soft outer cover of the fruits are crushed and soaked in the water. The black coloured water is used as dye. The wood is used for furniture for its durability and colour.
30	<i>Litsea cubeba</i> (Lour.) Pers.	<i>Shiingshaar</i>	Lauraceae	Tree	Flower and seed	The fresh flowers and seed are used as used as spice in vegetable chutney.
31	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> (L.) J Pres.	<i>Jaerhing</i>	Lauraceae	Tree	Bark	The dry bark is used as spice in cooking curry. It is also used to treat bad mouth odour by chewing the bark.
32	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> (Buch.-Ham.) T.Nees & C.H.Eberm.	<i>Tespata</i>	Lauraceae	Tree	leaves	The fresh or dried leaves are used as spice in cooking curry.
33	<i>Pogostemon parviflorus</i> Benth.	<i>Shanggarei</i>	Lamiaceae	Shrub	Leaves	The leaves are boiled with starchy rice water and washed the hair to treat dandruff and hair fall.

34	<i>Perilla frutescens</i> (L.) Britton	Rikneeng	Lamiaceae	Herbs	Leaf & inflorescence	Used as spice in curry and chutney and used to cure cold and cough, tonsil.
35	<i>Ocimum africanum</i> Lour.	Akwa rikneeng	Lamiaceae	Herbs	Leaf & iflorescence	Used as spice in curry and chutney. It is also used to cure cold and cough, tonsil
36	<i>Albizia chinensis</i> (Osbeck) Merr.	Ruwphoph	Fabaceae	Tree	Root- Bark,	The bark and roots are crushed, Shocked and drained in the intended area of the river to stupefy the fish. To make it more affected, this plant is mixed with the root of Jaerii (<i>Milletia parchycarpa</i> Benth.).
37	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.f.	Teak	Lamiaceae	Tree	stem	Wood is used as pillar, plank, frame in house construction.
38	<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> L.	Enthuur Evaar	Malvaceae	shrub	Fruit & Leaves	Fibre obtained from stem bark is used for making rope to tie the plant materials.
39	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Chinariii	Malvaceae	Shrub	Whole plant	The plants are grown in boundaries of houses for fencing of homogenous ones.
40	<i>Hibiscus acetosella</i> Welw. ex Hiern.	Enthuur eshaen	Malvaceae	Shrubs	Fruit & Leaves	The fresh fruit or dry calyx is boiled and used as traditional herbal drinks after food for digestion.
41	<i>Gossypium arboreum</i> L.	Lashing	Malvaceae	Shrub	Fruits	Used for making threat to weave clothes. Soft fibre is used for stuffing pillows, mattresses, cushion etc. It is a main source of threads for weaving cloths.
42	<i>Hibiscus abelmoschus</i> L.	Chinariii edii	Malvaceae	Shrub	bark	Fibre obtained from stem bark is used for making rope to tie the plant materials.
43	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Enthuur	Malvaceae	Shrub	bark	Fibre obtained from stem bark is used for making rope.
44	<i>Acacia pruineseens</i> Kurz.	Taepuung	Mimosaceae	Woody climber	Fruit	Fruit is crushed and shocked in water. The juice is used as shampoo and detergent.
45	<i>Ensete glaucum</i> (Roxb.) Cheesman	Changkiir	Musaceae	shrub	Stem & flower	The stem is cooked with meet during functions and festivals and the flower is used as chutney.
46	<i>Musa acuminata</i> Colla.	Naachang	Musaceae	Shrub	Stem & fruit	The stem is cooked with meat during functions and festivals and the flower is used as chutney.
47	<i>Musa balbisiana</i> Colla.	Lampa nachang	Musaceae	shrub	Leaves	During functions and festivals leaves used as plate or wrapper.
48	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	Meehna	Musaceae	Tree	Whole plant	The leave is also used as plate or wrapper in all socio-cultural functions. The Plant was used in all cultural function by planting at the

						entrance gate of the venue. The stem, flowers and fruits are edible.
49	<i>Oxalis latifolia</i> Kunth	<i>Pukcheeng</i>	Oxalidaceae	creeper	Whole plant	The plant is boiled with starchy rice water and used as shampoo for hairball and dandruff
50	<i>Milletia pachycarpa</i> Benth.	<i>Jaerii</i>	Fabaceae	Climber	Bark of root	The plant is mostly used for community fishing for its effectiveness in stupefying the fish. The extract from the crushed roots is run into the identified area of the river.
51	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.	<i>Rimpeeh</i>	Pedaliaceae	Shrub	seed	Seeds are used in preparation of sticky rice cake during socio-cultural functions and festivals.
52	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> Sarg.	<i>Mashaar</i>	Pinaceae	Tree	Leaves	Woods are used as planks in the construction of traditional house. Dry leaves are used as material for mattress.
53	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	<i>Buwshae</i>	Poaceae	Shrub	seed	Prepared indigenous alcoholic beverages Traditional rice beer called 'Zuw' is prepared from rice.
54	<i>Coix lacryma jobi</i> L.	<i>Nii-em</i>	Poaceae	shrub	Grain	Grains are used as main ingredients in the preparation of alcoholic beverages.
55	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> (Roxb.) Nees	<i>Ithii ruw</i>	poaceae	Shrubs	Culm	The culm is used for the handle of agricultural tools like hoe, knife, spade, spear etc for its thick culm and prominent nodes. Used as frames in house construction.
56	<i>Phyllostachys bambusoides</i> Madake.	<i>Ruwvah</i>	Poaceae	shrubs	culm	The culm is flattened by beating and used as wall and floor in construction of traditional house. Fermented bamboo shoot is used as spice. Used for making bamboo cup due to thin wall, straight and long internodes during cultural festival & functions. Bamboo flutes
57	<i>Bambusa nana</i> Roxb.	<i>Khor-ruw</i>	Poaceae	shrub	culm	Used for housing and handicraft
58	<i>Bambusa pallida</i> Munro.	<i>Ruwfhuw</i>	Poaceae	shrub	culm	Used for housing and handicraft
59	<i>Bambusa tulda</i> Roxb.	<i>Ruwmah</i>	Poaceae	shrub	culm	The culm is flattened by beating and used as wall and floor in construction of traditional house. Used for handicraft.
60	<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.)P.Beauv.	<i>Mandii</i>	Poaceae	shrub	leaves	The leaves is used as thatch for roofing traditional house.
61	<i>Zanthoxylum rhetsa</i> (Roxb.) DC.	<i>Bajuwr ynlor</i>	Rutaceae	Tree	Seed	Aromatic & Extensively used as Spice with tingling sensation on the tongue

62	<i>Zanthoxylum laetum</i> Drake	<i>Bajuwr edii</i>	Rutaceae	Tree	Leaves	Aromatic & Extensively used as Spice
63	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i> DC	<i>Shiinii</i>	Rutaceae	shrub	fruits, Leaves,	Aromatic & Extensively used as Spice with tingling sensation on the tongue
64	<i>Citrus latipes</i> (Swingle) Tanaka	<i>Shiirphoph</i>	Rutaceae	Tree	Fruit	The outer layer of the fruit and the leaves are added to curry as spice
65	<i>Canthium gracilipes</i> Kurz.	<i>Rampa haepi</i>	Rubiaceae	Tree	Root	The fruit is crushed and runs into the river to stupefy the fished. It is usually mean to be used in the shallow water. To make it more effective, either Jaerii or Ruwphoph is added.
66	<i>Capsicum chinense</i> Jacq.	<i>Brosfhuw</i>	Solanaceae	shrub	Fruit	Fresh and dried powdered are used as spice in Curry. The crushed chillies is the main ingredient for making chutney.
67	<i>Capsicum annuum</i> L.	<i>Brosedii</i>	Solanaceae	shrub	Fruit	Fresh and dried powdered are used as spice in Curry. The crushed chillies is the main ingredient for making chutney.
68	<i>Houttuynia cordata</i> Thunb.	<i>Toningkok</i>	Saururaceae	herb	Whole plant	Used as spice & as fresh herbal garnish in chutney for taste and flavour.
69	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L.) O. Kuntze.	<i>Rampa chaa</i>	Theaceae	Shrub	leaves	Leaves are crushed and dried. The dried leaves are used as traditional beverages.
70	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	<i>Ering Paar</i>	Verbenaceae	shrub	Whole plant	The plants are grown in boundaries of houses and village for fencing of homogenous ones. This is the most commonly used plant as bio-fencing.
71	<i>Alpinia nigra</i> (Gaetn.) Burt.	<i>Chaekho</i>	Zingiberaceae	shrub	Rhizome, flower	Crushed Rhizome and boiled flowers are added to dried meet chutney as spice for flavour
72	<i>Curcuma amada</i> Roxb.	<i>Chuwhae</i>	Zingiberaceae	shrub	Rhizome & flower	Crushed Rhizome is added raw vegetable chutney as spice for flavour & steamed flower is make chutney with river fish.
73	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	<i>Jinghaang</i>	Zingiberaceae	herbs	Rhizome	Dried rhizome powder is used as spice. leaves are used for cooking small river fishes by wrapping and roasted in the hot ash call 'Nganam'.
74	<i>Zingiber montanum</i> (J.König) Link ex A. Dietr.	<i>Lamshiig</i>	Zingiberaceae	Herbs	Rhizome	Rhizome is crushed and used as spice.
75	<i>Curcuma amarissima</i> L. Roscoe.	<i>Aetang</i>	Zingiberaceae	Herbs	Leaves & flower	Leaves are used as traditional packaging materials. Flowers are edible

Table 2 Plants used by *Moyon* tribe in socio-cultural importance

Sl. No.	Socio-cultural uses of plants	No. of plants	Plant used
1	Traditional spice	17	1. <i>Eryngium foetidum</i> , 2. <i>Zingiber montanum</i> , 3. <i>Curcuma longa</i> , 4. <i>Curcuma amada</i> , 5. <i>Litsea cubeba</i> , 6. <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> , 7. <i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> ., 8. <i>Perilla frutescens</i> , 9. <i>Ocimum africanum</i> , 10. <i>Zanthoxylum rhetsa</i> , 11. <i>Zanthoxylum laetum</i> , 12. <i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i> , 13. <i>Citrus latipes</i> , 14. <i>Capsicum chinense</i> , 15. <i>Capsicum annum</i> , 16. <i>Houttuynia cordata</i> , 17. <i>Alpinia nigra</i> ,
2	House construction	11	1. <i>Calamus latifolius</i> , 2. <i>Castanopsis armata</i> , 3. <i>Entada gigas</i> , 4. <i>Tectona grandis</i> , 5. <i>Pinus roxburghii</i> , 6. <i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> , 7. <i>Phyllostachys bambusoides</i> , 8. <i>Bambusa nana</i> , 9. <i>Bambusa pallida</i> , 10. <i>Bambusa tulda</i> , 11. <i>Imperata cylindrica</i> ,
3	Edible plants used in socio-cultural festivals	7	1. <i>Dioscorea alata</i> , 2. <i>Dioscorea japonica</i> , 3. <i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> , 4. <i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i> , 5. <i>Ensete glaucum</i> , 6. <i>Sesamum indicum</i> , 7. <i>Musa cuminata</i> ,
4	Shampoo & detergent	6	1. <i>Spondias pinnata</i> , 2. <i>Costus speciosus</i> , 3. <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> , 4. <i>Pogostemon parviflorus</i> , 5. <i>Acacia pruinoseens</i> , 6. <i>Oxalis latifolia</i> ,
5	Traditional drinks & beverages	5	1. <i>Rhus chinensis</i> , 2. <i>Hibiscus acetosella</i> , 3. <i>Oryza sativa</i> , 4. <i>Coix lacryma jobi</i> , 5. <i>Camellia sinensis</i> ,
6	Bio-fencing	5	1. <i>Justicia adhatoda</i> , 2. <i>Phlogacanthus thysiformis</i> , 3. <i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> , 4. <i>Hibiscus rosa- sinensis</i> , 5. <i>Lantana camara</i> ,
7	Plants used for fishing	5	1. <i>Senegalia rugata</i> , 2. <i>Gnetum montanum</i> , 3. <i>Albizia chinensis</i> , 4. <i>Milletia pachycarpa</i> , 5. <i>Canthium gracilipes</i> ,
8	Fibre & Thread	4	1. <i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> , 2. <i>Gossypium arboreum</i> , 3. <i>Hibiscus abelmoschus</i> , 4. <i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> ,
9	Handicraft	4	<i>Calamus floribundus</i> , <i>Calamus jenkinsianus</i> , <i>Calamus leptospadix</i> , 4. <i>Calamus tenuis</i> ,
10	Ornamentals flowers used during festivals	3	1. <i>Dendrobium infudibulum</i> , 2. <i>Canna indica</i> , 3. <i>Rhododendron arboretum</i> ,
11	wrapper/traditional packaging	3	1. <i>Curcuma amarissima</i> , 2. <i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L., 3. <i>Musa balbisiana</i> ,
12	Ingredient for fermented food	2	1. <i>Alocasia macrorrhizos</i> , 2. <i>Albizia myriophylla</i>
13	Insect repellent	1	<i>Tagetes erecta</i>
14	Traditional dye	1	<i>Juglans regia</i>
15	Agriculture tools	1	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> ,

Figure 2 No of plants and their parts used by *Moyon* tribe in Socio-cultural importance

Figure 3 No of plants and their habitat used by *Moyon* tribe in Socio-cultural importance

4. Conclusion

The study of Ethnobotany of Moyon tribe gives more emphasis on socio-religious plants will help in the preparation of socio-religious databases. The use of ethnobotanical tools is a very new approach here in analysis of Moyon socio-religious from Chandel and Tengnoupal Districts of Manipur State. The high consensus obtained from the healers underlines their well-defined tradition and could guide in selection of plants as potent candidates for bioprospecting and natural product studies. The traditional knowledge of herbal knowledge practiced among the *Moyon* community of the 17 villages surrounding the two districts should be conserved through its documentation before it is lost from the respective *Moyon* societies forever. It will also protect the Intellectual property rights (IPR) of the *Moyon* community of the study area. The socio-religious claim of this study has to be exploited further for developing a new information base to validate and conservation for sustainable use.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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